

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Milestones

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ETrP	ELIXIR Training Platform
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Executive Summary

This deliverable is a [publicly available, user-friendly guide](#) on how to use Bioschemas for training events and materials, utilizing the [ELIXIR Training Lesson template](#) as foundational infrastructure. The objective is to provide the first comprehensive guide on Bioschemas annotation for training events and materials, addressing the current lack of such a resource. The guide is built on existing [ELIXIR training material about TeSS](#), derived from the paper "Making Bioinformatics Training Events and Material More Discoverable Using TeSS, the ELIXIR Training Portal" (<https://doi.org/10.1002/cpzi.682>), and [technical documentation](#) from the Bioschemas portal. It starts with foundational knowledge for non-technical end users, covers intermediate topics of annotation using static site renderers like mkdocs and Jekyll, and concludes with annotation of training material hosted on the popular WordPress Content Management System. The authors of this guide feel the need for future alignment and collaboration with the members of the BioHackathon 2024 project 10, "[Bioschemas for Mortals](#)," since a survey executed during this BioHackathon project identified a strong need for such a guide. Furthermore, participants of the TeSS club and members of the Bioschemas community contributed to the current content of the guide.

This guide provides background information about the technical components to use Bioschemas markup for training assets. This will assist existing and new technical maintainers in onboarding and provide clear instructions on using these technical website renderers together with Bioschemas markup. The resource and its documentation are designed to be open, easily maintained, and tailored for a non-technical audience, promoting better adoption among training coordinators and providers across the Nodes. The integration of Bioschemas markup into ELIXIR-branded training events and materials will facilitate automatic population when in use, enhancing accessibility and sustainability.

Outcomes and Impacts of the deliverable

The output for this deliverable was first drafted in Summer 2024. The course delves into the specifics of Bioschemas annotation, demonstrating how to apply it to an HTML page to enhance discoverability and interoperability. Following this introductory part, the guide explores the integration of Bioschemas with popular static site generators and content management systems, including Jekyll, Mkdocs, and WordPress. Each section provides practical examples and step-by-step instructions to ensure learners can effectively implement Bioschemas annotations in their own projects. This training is designed to equip participants with the skills needed to improve the visibility and accessibility of their training content on the web.

Figure 1: ELIXIR Bioschemas for Training Guide¹

Subsequent feedback has been requested by the members of the ELIXIR Training Platform (October 2024 and November 2024) as well as from the members of the TeSS club at various meetings. This milestone incorporates feedback from the TeSS team and the 'Bioschemas for Mortals' project, which identified key challenges for non-technical users and priority areas for improvement (Note: BioHackrXiv paper is coming soon).

As a result, this work highlights synergies and cross-relationships with the BioHackathon 2024 project, further aligning efforts to address user needs effectively.

The [first version](#) published as training material within the ELIXIR Training GitHub organisation using the ELIXIR Lesson template was released on the 30th of December 2024. Further workshops are planned in 2025 to extend the current content (e.g., with other Content Management Systems used for training material) supporting the work from the Biohackathon 2024 project 10. We also aim to add this material on the ELIXIR Training SPLASH website under the focus topic 'FAIR training'.

¹ <https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-TrP-Bioschemas/>